

Active Vibration, Two-tone, and Multitone Suppression in Two Basal Locations in the Gerbil Cochlea

C. Elliott Strimbu^{1, a)} and Elizabeth S. Olson^{1, 2}

¹*Department of Otolaryngology, Columbia University Vagelos College of Physicians and Surgeons
P&S 11-452, 630 West 168th Street
New York, NY 10031
USA.*

²*Department of Biomedical Engineering, Columbia University
1210 Amsterdam Ave.
New York, NY 10027
USA.*

^{a)}Corresponding author: ces2243@cumc.columbia.edu

Abstract. Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) has revolutionized the understanding of vibrations within the Organ of Corti. Most prominently, the technique has shown that the outer hair cell (OHC) region vibrates with higher amplitudes and distinct tuning relative to the basilar membrane (BM), and exhibits compressive nonlinearity at frequencies well below that location's best frequency (BF). Here, a series of low-side suppression experiments has been performed to probe activity in gerbil cochleae at two basal BF locations, the 25 kHz location in turn one and 45 kHz in the cochlear hook. Responses were measured to: (1) pure tone, "frequency sweep", stimuli (2) the same frequency sweep but in the presence of an intense low-side suppressor, 100 dB SPL at 3 kHz; and (3) multitone zwuis tone complexes covering the same frequencies and at approximately the same effective SPLs. $2f_1 - f_2$ distortion product otoacoustic emissions were measured at the same times and used to gauge the general cochlear condition. At the 25 kHz location, the low-side suppressor linearized the BM responses and the peak vanished, with the gain tuning curves resembling those of a passive cochlea. OHC responses were also linearized by the suppressor, and exhibited a steep fall-off near BF. At the 45 kHz location the suppressor linearized sub-BF responses and reduced BF responses but the peak remained. At this location the reticular lamina (RL) region is identifiable, and the BF vibrations of the RL-region showed higher amplitudes than the BM, like the OHC-region, but smaller responses and linear growth in the sub-BF region. In the presence of the low-side suppressor, sub-BF RL-region vibrations were unaffected, and the amplitude of the BF peak was reduced.

INTRODUCTION

It is well established that in healthy cochleae the basilar membrane (BM) responses are sharply tuned and compressively nonlinear in a narrow region about each longitudinal location's best frequency (BF). This sharp tuning and nonlinearity arise from the active process or cochlear amplifier which selectively boosts the vibrations evoked by low-level sounds. Over the past decade or so, new results from optical coherence tomography (OCT) have revealed that the vibrations of other structures within the organ of Corti (OoC) are qualitatively different from those at the BM (BM). Because an OCT instrument is able to image in two and three dimensions, with ~ 5 -micron-level resolution at very nearly same time and at the same location as the vibration measurements are made it is now possible to map the vibrations more precisely onto anatomical locations than was typically possible in the past. At the same time, the motion of structures within the OoC are complex with components that can lie along each of the organ's three anatomical axes: the longitudinal, radial, and transverse directions. An OCT system, or any interferometer, can only measure the one dimensional projection of the motion in the direction parallel to the light beam; which in general is not aligned in a particular anatomical direction.

Because the cochlear amplifier relies on multiple feedback mechanisms working in synchrony to drive each longitudinal section of the OoC, understanding the internal OoC vibrations seems essential. In the base of the gerbil cochlea, the outer hair cell (OHC) region, extending from approximately the OHC/Deiters' cell junctions to near the reticular lamina (RL) vibrates with a larger amplitude and distinct tuning than the BM as shown in Figures 2 and 3 [1, 2, 3, 4]. The large amplitudes cause this region to appear as a "hotspot" in two dimensional vibration maps [1].

In these experiments, the active internal OoC vibrations were probed by comparing the responses to pure tones, pure tones in the presence of an intense low side suppressor, and zwuis multitone stimuli.

FIGURE 1. (A) A schematic diagram of the organ of Corti with important anatomical features labeled: AZ and PZ, arcuate and pectinate zones of the BM; TC: Tunnel of Corti; OHCs: Outer Hair Cells, DCs: Deiters' Cells; OT: Outer Tunnel; TM: Tectorial Membrane; HCs: Hensen's Cells. Created with BioRender.com. The cochlea's natural longitudinal, transverse and radial directions are indicated by the arrows. (B) A Bscan taken at the 45 kHz place in the gerbil cochlea with a few anatomical features marked: BM; TC/SN: Tunnel of Corti and Space of Nuell; OT; and OHCs. The fluid filled spaces, the Tunnel of Corti/Space of Nuell, and the Outer Tunnel are important anatomical landmarks for identifying structures within the OoC and the OT is especially prominent in the base of the cochlea. (C) and (D) Two slices of a volumetric image taken at the 25 kHz place in a gerbil cochlea. The Bscan in (C) is in the quasi-radial/quasi-transverse direction and is the usual plane in which vibration measurements are taken. Scale bar: 50 μm . The Bscan in (D) lies in an orthogonal plane along the quasi-longitudinal/quasi-transverse direction. It is apparent from (D) that the vibrometry at this place is primarily in the longitudinal anatomical direction. The projections of the OCT beam in the longitudinal, radial, and transverse directions in this example are $(l, r, t) = (.86, -.40, .31)$. Experiment #1000. (E) and (F) are two slices from a volume scan taken at the 45 kHz place. The Bscans in E and F show that at this place, the imaging and vibrometry are primarily in the transverse anatomical direction. The projections of the OCT beam in the longitudinal, radial, and transverse directions are $(l, r, t) = (-.53, -.097, .84)$. Experiment #996.

METHODS

Details of the surgical procedures, OCT imaging and vibrometry, and DPOAE measurements have been described in detail in previous publications [2, 3, 5, 6]. OCT recordings were taken with the instrument synchronized to the AD/DA system with a nominal sampling rate of 130 kHz (130208.3333 S/s). All experiments were performed in accordance with policies laid out by the Columbia University IACUC.

OoC vibrations were measured through the intact round window membrane in the base of the cochlea at either the ~ 25 kHz location, where the view is primarily longitudinal with a significant transverse component, or deep in the hook region at the ~ 45 kHz location where the view is typically primarily transverse. Figure 1 shows Bscans taken in two orthogonal planes within the OoC at the two places. The vibrations were measured in a two-dimensional pattern in the quasi-radial direction (in the xz plane of the Bscan in Figure 1C) with a spacing of $\sim 14 - 20 \mu\text{m}$ between each quasi-radial location or slice. Results are presented as response and gain tuning curves, with phase referenced to ear canal pressure. At each longitudinal location, a complete set of vibration measurements consisted of: (1) the responses to pure tone stimuli, which is referred to as a "frequency sweep", (2) the same pure tones in the presence of an intense low-side suppressor, 3 kHz at 100 dB SPL, which is referred to as a "sweep + suppressor", and (3) a set of zwuis tone complexes. Before and after each vibration measurement, the OCT took two dimensional Bscans and we used false-color (sweep Bscan in magenta and sweep + suppressor Bscan in yellow) composite images of these to assess the stability of the preparation and also compared Bscans from different runs to compensate for any drift if needed. See Figures 4G and 5G for examples of this. At each longitudinal location we also took a 3-D volumetric scan to determine the projection of the OCT beam in the longitudinal, radial, and transverse directions [6] and also recorded a DPOAE-audiogram to accompany the vibration measurements.

The sweep and sweep + suppressor consisted of 32 discrete frequencies each of which was presented for 8192

FIGURE 2. Responses to tones and zwuis tone complexes at the 25 kHz place. (A) The DPOAE-audiogram taken before the vibration measurements indicate that the cochlea was healthy. (B) A Bscan showing the cross section in which the measurements were made. Scale bar: 50 μm . The orange and blue markers indicate the locations on the BM and in the OHC-region whose vibrations are shown below. In this experiment the projections of the OCT beam in the longitudinal, radial, and transverse directions were $(l, r, t) = (.89, .16, .42)$. (C) BM gain and phase in response to pure tone frequency sweeps. The vibrations are plotted in shades of blue with darker hues indicating higher SPLs. As in all classic BM measurements, the vibrations are compressively nonlinear in a region around the location's BF and linear at lower frequencies, although the lower SPL vibrations were within the noise floor in this example. (D) OHC-region gain and phase. The vibrations are plotted in shades of orange. Note that the OHC-region's gain is higher than that of the BM's at all frequencies with the ratio varying from $\sim 10 \times$ higher at low frequencies to $\sim 3 \times$ in the BF-region. In response to single tones, the OHC vibrations are linear in the sub-BF band. (E) BM vibrations in response to a zwuis tone complex, covering a similar effective dynamic range. The tuning curve is quite similar to that in (C). (F) OHC-region responses to the zwuis complex. As in the single-tone measurement, OHC vibrations are higher in amplitude than the BM's; with the multitone stimuli they are compressively nonlinear across the entire frequency band tested. Note that at higher SPLs, ~ 67 -80 dB, the vibrations are suppressed relative to the single tone responses. Experiment #1005.

samples or ~ 63 ms including a 1 ms rise/fall time, for a total recording time of ~ 2 seconds. In the zwuis recordings, N frequencies (typically 35 in these experiments) were presented simultaneously for ~ 1 second and chosen such that the stimulus contains no harmonics, nor intermodulation distortion products up to third order. Each frequency component was assigned a random phase $0 < \phi < 2\pi$ so the total sound pressure level was $\sim 10 \log N$ dB SPL higher than each of the primaries. For each of the two longitudinal regions, the bandwidths of the sweep and zwuis stimuli were chosen to cover the appropriate range. Because the 25 kHz location is more sensitive, the stimuli were played at lower levels when recording from that location. Sound pressure levels are indicated in the figures and captions.

RESULTS

The experiments have been performed in a number of animals and the results were consistent, although there was more variation across the experiments performed at the 45 kHz place. All cochleae tested had robust and reasonably stable DPOAE-audiograms and vibrations were consistent with a healthy cochlear amplifier. As background, Figures 2 and 3 show responses to pure tones and the zwuis multitone complexes at the 25 and 45 kHz locations. Results of the low-side suppression from the 25 and 45 kHz places are presented and discussed separately below.

Low-side and Multitone Suppression at the 25 kHz Place

Figure 4 shows results from the 25 kHz place. Tuning curves and phase (referenced to the ear canal pressure) are shown for the sweeps, sweeps + suppressor, and for the zwuis multitone stimuli. Data are shown for the BM and two locations in the OHC-region with the recording locations shown in the Bscan in panel (G). At this tonotopic place, the OHC-region vibrations are rather stereotyped [1, 2, 3, 4] and the precise locations chosen for analysis do not affect the qualitative conclusions. The top columns (A) – (C) show the displacement (top row), gain (middle row), and

FIGURE 3. Responses to tones and tone complexes at the 45 kHz place. The layout of this figure is similar to the previous one. At the 45 kHz place, the RL surface is well delineated in the Bscan and its vibrations can be separated from the OHC-region. The BM and OHC vibrations are plotted using the same color scheme as Figure (2) and RL vibrations are plotted in shades of violet. Panel G shows the pronounced trough in the OHC-region vibrations at 80 dB and around the BF-region. This trough in the amplitude is accompanied by a phase lift at 30 kHz and can be understood as being due to a reduction in the internal OHC vibrations that are out of phase with the BM motion [4]. Note that the RL vibrations qualitatively resemble those of the BM in showing linear responses in the sub-BF band in response to the zwiis tones. The scale bar in (B) is 58 μm and the projections of the OCT beam in the longitudinal, radial, and transverse directions were $(l, r, t) = (-.71, -.38, .59)$. Experiment #1009.

phase referenced to the ear canal pressure (bottom row) evoked by the sweeps (plotted in shades of orange) and the sweeps + suppressor (plotted in shades of blue). SPLs are indicated by the legend to the right of (C). The rightmost panel in the third row shows the phase difference, OHC-region - BM measured in response to the frequency sweep, plotted in green to grey. (D) – (F) show the tuning curves and phase evoked by the multitone stimuli with the sweep + suppressor curves overlaid.

In response to both the sweep and zwiis stimuli, the BM responses were compressively nonlinear in a region around the BF (middle panels of A and D). In contrast the OHC region's vibrations exhibited a broad-band nonlinearity extending well below the BF of the particular longitudinal place in response to the multitone stimulus (top panels of E and F). This nonlinearity vanished *post mortem* evincing sub-BF activity [1, 3]. When stimulated by the zwiis complexes, the OHC vibrations exhibited hypercompression in the BF-region at the highest SPLs; that is, the amplitude precipitously falls off in the BF-region at the highest SPL (or equivalently, the responses become low-pass in character with a corner frequency somewhat below the BF).

In the presence of the low-side suppressor, the vibration amplitudes decreased at all three locations with the amplitudes at the lowest SPLs (45 – 55 dB) falling into the noise level. At the higher levels, the responses were linearized and showed a loss of tuning in the BF-region, generally resembling those of a passive cochlea. At the BM, gain curves evoked by the sweep + suppressor overlapped those evoked by the highest level sweeps at 80 dB SPL, a level where the responses are expected to be dominated by the passive mechanical properties of the OoC. Within the OHC-region, the responses in the presence of the suppressor fall into roughly two distinct frequency bands. For frequencies well below the BF, the tuning curves showed a $\sim 5 - 10$ -fold decrease in amplitude indicating that the OHC-region vibrations are indeed active in that frequency band. Within the BF-region, the vibration amplitude fell off significantly more quickly than the amplitude of the 80 dB sweeps alone. The bottom columns (D) – (F) show the zwiis multitone responses measured at nearby points with the sweep + suppressor responses plotted on the same axes. In general, the sweep + suppressor gain curves aligned well the highest level zwiis, 80 dB, zwiis vibrations (middle row of Columns (D) – (F) for all three locations.

Low-side and Multitone Suppression at the 45 kHz Place

Figure 5 shows vibration tuning curves at the 45 kHz place. At this location, the RL is well delineated and its vibrations were qualitatively more similar to those of the BM rather than the OHC-region, showing nonlinear growth only in the BF-region [4]. At the 45 kHz place the OHC-region's vibrations exhibited a trough, or a wide band-stop region, in the responses (middle panel of B and top panel of E) around the BF, which seems to be due to a cancellation of BM and internal OHC motion [4]. Because the 45 kHz place recordings are primarily in the transverse direction this behavior is relatively unaffected by motion in the longitudinal and/or radial directions. In the presence of the suppressor, the vibrations fell into the noise floor at the lower SPLs for all structures. BM, responses, column (A), showed nearly linear growth at the higher levels except for a few points in the BF-region where there was some persistent nonlinearity. In the OHC-region, column (B), the responses showed a loss of amplitude in the sub-BF region, revealing the presence of activity there. Near BF, the OHC vibrations fell into the noise level except at the highest SPL. RL vibrations, column (C), were mostly within the noise level in the sub-BF region and there was, in this example, an increase in the RL motion at the high stimulus levels around the BF. All three positions retained a residual BF peak at higher SPLs in the presence of the suppressor tone, with the BM and OHC-region showing amplitude reduction relative to the sweeps. The phase differences, OHC – BM and RL – BM are plotted in panel (H), again in shades of green to grey with the OHC – BM in thicker lines. The phase lifts in the OHC-region's vibrations, bottom panels of columns (B) and (E), appear to occur when the overall motion of the OHC (composed of OHC internal motion + BM) transitions from moving $\sim \frac{1}{2}$ cycle out of phase with the BM, to moving in phase with the BM [4]. Similar to the 25 kHz place, the sweep + suppressor responses (Figure 5, columns (D)–(F)) show less overall gain than the zwuis responses at most SPLs; although in this example, the highest level zwuis gain curve was somewhat lower than the sweep + suppressor curves.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

The “classic” view of cochlear amplification states that the vibrations of BM are actively boosted in the BF-region where the output is compressively nonlinear and sharply tuned. It is now apparent that vibrations of the internal structures of the OoC also exhibit activity but with different amplitude and tuning than those of the BM vibrations. We have probed this activity at two longitudinal places in the cochlear base by comparing the responses to pure tone frequency sweeps, the same sweeps in the presence of an intense low-side suppressor, and zwuis multitone complexes. In the cochlear base, the OHC-region's vibrations show an overall active gain or amplification across the entire frequency band when comparing the sweeps to the sweeps + suppressor. This active gain is present in the sub-BF band in spite of the linear growth when stimulating with pure tones. In response to the multitone zwuis stimuli this activity manifests as a broad-band nonlinearity that is pronounced in the low frequency region.

Dong and Olson studied the effects of two-tone suppression near the 25 kHz place using custom-built dual sensors which simultaneously monitored the scala tympani (ST) pressure, that closely follows BM motion, and the local cochlear microphonic potential [7]. In part of that study, the authors used a low-side suppression paradigm similar to the one used here. The effects of the suppressor tone on ST pressure were similar to what was observed in the BM responses in this study: with the suppressor tone, the gain of ST pressure became linearized and showed a loss of amplitude and peak in the BF region, while the responses in the sub-BF band were largely unaffected. Moreover, the changes in the local cochlear microphonic in the presence of the suppressor resembled the changes we observed in the gain of OHC-region responses: linearization of the gain at all frequencies, a loss of amplitude and peak in the BF-region, but also loss of amplification in the sub-BF band.

Dewey *et al.* studied the effects of two-tone suppression on both BM and RL vibrations in apical regions of the mouse cochlea, close to the 9 – 9.5 kHz BF place [8]. The authors found that while the RL traveling wave was amplified over a broad frequency band, the amplification only accumulated near the peak, or BF-region, similar to where the BM vibrations are also boosted, arguing against a more global amplification mechanism.

Cho and Puria [9] have also performed OCT-based vibrometry in the hook region (~ 45 kHz BF) of the gerbil cochlea. They compared healthy and *post mortem* recordings at the OHC/DC junction and RL and found a loss of gain *post mortem* [9], similar to what we observe with the suppressor tone in the low frequency, sub-BF band. However, in the *post mortem* responses measured by Cho and Puria, the BF peak was nearly eliminated, whereas in the responses reported here, at the 45 kHz region a nonlinear BF peak persisted in the presence of the low-side suppressor, but at a reduced level. The suppressor did eliminate the BF peak in the 25 kHz region.

FIGURE 4. Low side suppression at the 25 kHz place. Columns (A) – (C) show the displacement, gain, and phase at the BM and two locations within the OHC region evoked by a frequency sweep (plotted in shades of orange) and the sweep + suppressor (plotted in shades of blue). In the presence of the suppressor, the vibrations of all structures fall into the noise floor at lower SPLs and became linearized with a loss of tuning at the higher levels. When suppressed, the high frequency fall-off, more closely resembles the unsuppressed low-level fall off rather than the more gradual, passive-like, 85 dB gain curves. Columns (D) – (F) show the vibrations at nearby points evoked by the zwiis complex with the results of the sweep + suppressor plotted on the same axes. The sweep + suppressor gain curves overlap with the zwiis curves at 80 dB for all three structures. (G) False-color composite Bscan showing the locations of the three recording locations; magenta channel: Bscan taken before the sweeps and yellow channel: scan taken before sweeps + suppressor. In this measurement set, it was necessary to shift the sweep+suppressor Bscan 20 μm in the lateral direction and the individual pixels/regions of interest were selected accordingly. Scale bar: 50 μm . The projections of the OCT beam in the longitudinal, radial, and transverse directions are $(l, r, t) = (.85, .17, .50)$. Panels (H) and (J) show the phase difference between the OHC-region or RL and the BM in response to the sweeps and zwiis tones, with the levels plotted in greens to grey. (I) shows the DPOAE-audiogram measured before these vibration data were taken. Experiment #1006.

FIGURE 5. Low side and multitone suppression at the 45 kHz place. The layout of this figure is similar to the previous one but with the explicit RL vibrations shown. Columns (A) – (C) show BM, OHC, and RL vibration tuning curves and phase in response to the sweep and sweep + suppressor stimuli. In the OHC region, the 85 dB sweep+suppressor aligned well with the 75 dB sweep. In general, vibrations in all three regions exhibited a residual peak in the BF region in the presence of the suppressor. Columns (D) – (E) show the responses at nearby point to the multitone stimuli with the sweep + suppressor curves overlaid. (G) False-color Bscan of the recording location. Scale bar: 58 μm . The projections of the OCT beam in the longitudinal, radial, and transverse directions are $(l, r, t) = (.46, -.28, .84)$. Panels (H) and (J) show the phase difference between the OHC-region or RL and the BM in response to the sweeps and zwiis tones, with the levels plotted in greens to grey with OHC-BM vibrations plotted in thick lines and RL-BM plotted in thin lines. Experiment #1007.

The role sub-BF nonlinearity plays in cochlear amplification is not fully understood. Recent modeling work has proposed that the cochlear amplifier may work through an area-based fluid pumping mechanism [10, 11] which would be consistent with the broad-band activity seen in the OHC-region vibrations. More generally, active motion in the OHC/DC area could play a role in feed-forward or regulatory mechanisms because the DCs each possess a phalangeal process that couples to the RL some two to four rows apart [12, 13]. Whatever the precise role, the cochlear amplifier involves a number of feedback and/or feed-forward mechanisms at each longitudinal cross-section that must operate in synchrony.

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QUESTIONS AND COMMENTS FROM THE DISCUSSION BOARD

James Dewey Hi Elliott & Lisa, Nice, clearly presented study of suppressive effects of different stimuli in basal regions of the gerbil cochlea. A few questions: 1) For the 25 kHz location, the near equivalence of the effects of the high-level low-frequency tone and the 80 dB SPL multi-tone stimuli is a satisfying result. Is it possible to compare the overall RMS amplitude of BM (and/or OHC) responses elicited by the low frequency suppressor and the highest-level multi-tone stimulus? I am wondering which is more intense (in terms of the vibrations that are relevant to OHC stimulation). 2) Do you ever observe short-term or long-term changes in sensitivity (or DPOAEs) after measuring the frequency sweeps with the 100 dB SPL suppressor tone?

C. Elliott Strimbu Hi James, Thanks for the comments and the detailed review. For your first question, we have not explicitly done the comparison between the highest SPL multi-tone (zwuis) and low frequency suppressor but we have all the data and it would be easy to look at these. As far as your second question, we have not explicitly looked at short-term threshold shifts after the sweep + suppressor measurements. It takes our OCT computer about 15 seconds to process and save a two second recording so all of the sweep + suppressor measurements went as, "two seconds of the tones (~63 ms each) + the low side suppressor followed by ~ 15 seconds of rest before the next recording started". We did not take a DPOAE recording after each sweep + suppressor measurement nor did we try to measure pure tone responses right after. My educated guess is that two seconds of the intense suppressor, even played repeatedly following the 15 seconds of rest, is not sufficient to cause short term threshold shifts; or at least, threshold

shifts that we could measure with our setup. We took data from each animal for several hours and the DPOAEs and mechanical responses were stable and relatively healthy throughout each experiment so there does not seem to be a cumulative effect of the suppressor; at least over the timescale of our experiments. For the sake of space, we did not show all the data in the MoH Proceeding. In my (somewhat limited) experience, the loud sound has to be presented for at least several minutes before there are measurable changes in the mechanical responses. Even when we took data at 4 – 5 levels, and 7 – 11 quasi-radial locations, and then from 3 – 6 longitudinal locations, this only amounts to maybe 5 – 10 minutes total with the loud suppressor spread out over several hours. I would assume this would not cause short term (or long term) threshold shifts; but using the OCT to look for threshold shifts/changes in the mechanical responses after a long-term exposure to loud sounds could be a very interesting experiment to try in the future. Regards, Elliott

Tianying Ren Hello, Elliott, Thank you for presenting so much valuable experimental data. I enjoyed reading your manuscript and attending your great talk! Your data in Figs. 4B, C, E, and F demonstrate that a loud low-frequency tone can suppress RL and OHC-region responses at all frequencies. This novel finding is comparable to a previous observation that RL vibration at low frequencies far below the BF is physiologically vulnerable (Fig. 2 by Ren *et al.* PNAS 2016). Another important result from your experiments is that the phase difference between the RL and BM vibration decreased with frequency (Figs. 4H and J). This data verified an unexpected result: the latency of the RL vibration is greater than that of the BM (He *et al.* eLife 2018). Since your novel data carry critical information for understanding cochlear amplification, a brief interpretation of the data could boost the impact of your paper. **C. Elliott Strimbu** Thanks for reading the manuscript and the comments and suggestions. I'm at the page limit so I can't really make too many additions to the manuscript as it is. We are looking at, and thinking about, the phase differences between the different structures carefully.